

FINITE ELEMENT PREDICTION OF EFFECT OF RIBBON SENSOR ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBRE/EPOXY WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an investigation into the effect of amorphous ribbon sensor on the mechanical properties of carbon fibre/epoxy (CF/epoxy) woven laminates. Finite Element (FE) unit cell techniques have been employed in conjunction with Hashin failure criterion to predict the effective elastic constants and failure strengths. The 2/2 twill weave unit cell has been adopted for validating the FE model against the experimental results. Reasonable agreement has been observed between the FE predicted and the experimental results.

Keywords: plain weave, twill weave, carbon fibre/epoxy woven composites, mechanical properties, embedded sensors effect, Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

INTRODUCTION

Compared to the unidirectional (UD) laminate composites, the woven fabrics have already attracted a huge interest into the industrial composite sector because of their balanced texture with high adaptability to structures and better through thickness mechanical properties. Moreover, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) being widely accepted as techniques to monitor the integrity of composite structures, weaving-in of sensors during the fabric production stage has been found to gain a lot of potential. In order to enhance the confidence in using woven composite structures, a suitable modelling approach has been performed to assess the effect of sensor's embedment on the overall performance of the woven composites. Furthermore, to predict the effective mechanical properties using FE techniques, the authors have adopted the homogenisation techniques to define the geometrical periodicity of the woven composite material. FE analyses have been carried out using ABAQUS CAE/Standard package [1]. The effective mechanical properties of the unit cell models containing the embedded sensors have been predicted and then compared to the equivalent models containing no sensors. It has been found that the FE modelled results of 2/2 twill weave unit cells are in reasonable agreement with experimental results. The investigation into the effect of the amorphous ribbon sensors on the mechanical performance of the Carbon-Fiber/Epoxy woven composites using FE analysis is presented in the following sections.

FE MODELLING APPROACH

General Modelling Methodology

The analytical representation of the constitutive properties of the woven composites is difficult due to the complexity of the weave's tow/wavy architecture. The complex geometry and structure coupled with the consideration of the failure modes of the composite structures makes it difficult and expensive to model. Therefore, the homogenisation techniques have been used by defining the geometrical periodicity of the weave structure, also known as "the unit cell". Employing such techniques, the mechanical behaviour of the complex woven heterogeneous composite structure would be defined with the effective FE predicted unit cell mechanical properties.

The FE model for the unit cell includes the configuration of yarns, filling the gap between warp and weft yarns with resin matrix, defining the yarn/resin properties, meshing and applying the appropriate boundary conditions. The predicted and validated unit cell elastic and strength properties are then used for global/complex structural modelling. A general modelling approach of such technique is illustrated in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Unit Cell Modelling Approach

Modelling Conditions

ABAQUS CAE/Standard package has been used for the unit cell investigations. The modelling conditions and assumptions are described in this section.

It has been assumed that the warp and weft of the weave structure have the same yarn geometry. A sinusoidal profile has been considered for the yarn path. The dimensions of the yarn cross section have been defined based on the microscopic analysis of the true weave pattern as shown in Figure 2. The cross section of the yarns has been chosen to be elliptical based on the evidence obtained from experimental microscopic investigations. The amorphous ribbon sensor attached to the yarns has been considered to be rectangular.

Figure 2 Section View of a Woven Composite Laminate (Courtesy of BVT)

After defining the geometry and periodic weave pattern of the woven laminate, a resin matrix block has been superimposed on the weave pattern to establish the requisite unit cell model. The meshed unit cell of plain weave structure is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3a shows the skeleton of the warp and weft yarns where as the Figure 3b shows the resin infused composite woven structure. For the prediction of the mechanical performance of the composite structure, tetrahedral elements C3D4 [1] have been employed due to the presence of irregularities in the gaps between the yarns and the resin parts.

a) Warp and Weft Yarns

b) Yarns and Matrix

Figure 3 Typical Plain Weave Unit Cell Model

The material orientations of the yarns (Figure 4) have been defined using the user subroutine ORIENT [1]. It can be observed that the principle axis (direction-1) of the yarn always follows the yarn path.

Figure 4 Local Material Orientations of Yarn with Elliptical Cross Section

To predict the axial and shear properties of the composite with and without sensors, the appropriate boundary conditions have been applied separately. DISP subroutine [1] has been employed to maintain the in-plane and/or the out-plane shear deformation. The undeformed (green frames) and deformed shapes under tensile and shear loading are displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Unit Cell Deformations under Tensile and Shear Loading

To model the unit cells, the yarns have been considered as orthotropic material whereas the resin matrix and sensors have been considered to have isotropic material properties. The linear elastic analysis has been carried out individually for both the unit cell models without and with sensors. The modelling parameters together with FE predicted results of the modelling are discussed in the following sections.

INFLUENCE OF SENSORS ON THE UNIT CELL

Modelling Parameters

Preliminary investigations on the influence/effect of sensors on the unit cell mechanical properties have been carried out on the plain weave structures. The configurations of the plain weave unit cell are listed in Table 1. In Table 1, l is the length, w is the width and h is the height of the plain weave unit cell. The yarn cross section is elliptical where the length of long axis is b and short axis is a . It can also be found from Table 1 that three sensor sizes have been considered for this investigation. Using the geometry considered in these models, the total volume fraction has been estimated to be 35%.

Table 1 Geometric Parameters (mm) of Plain Weave Unit Cell

	l	w	h	a	b	
Unit cell	10.28	10.28	1	N/A	N/A	
Yarn	Sinusoidal path			0.34	3.72	
Sensor-1	Following the yarn path		1	0.05	N/A	N/A
Sensor-2			1	0.1	N/A	N/A
Sensor-3			3.72	0.05	N/A	N/A

The amorphous ribbon sensors have been assumed to be attached on the yarn surfaces in the middle as shown in Figure 6 for the plain weave unit cell. The material properties provided by manufacturers and used in the modelling are listed in Table 2.

Figure 6 Typical Sensor Positions in the Plain Weave Unit Cell

Table 2 Elastic Material Properties in Unit Cell Model (moduli in GPa)

	E_1	E_2	E_3	G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}	ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
Yarn	162	14.9	14.9	5.7	5.7	5.4	0.28	0.28	0.38
Matrix	3.1			1.12			0.39		
Sensor	100			38.46			0.3		

Predicted Results of the Plain Weave Unit Cell

Predicted elastic properties for the different type of sensor sizes in the unit cell are compared against the normal woven composite structure containing no sensor (also called as No-sensor model). The influences of the sensor size on the elastic properties of the unit cell are listed in Table 3 to Table 5.

Table 3 Comparison of No-sensor to Sensor-1 Unit Cell (moduli in GPa)

	No-sensor	Sensor 1 x 0.05 (mm)	Difference %
E ₁	34.42	35.38	2.79
E ₂	34.54	34.98	1.27
E ₃	6.60	6.70	1.52
G ₁₂	3.70	4.01	8.53
G ₁₃	1.49	1.51	1.34
G ₂₃	1.45	1.48	2.01
v ₁₂	0.048	0.051	6.25

Table 4 Comparison of No-sensor to Sensor-2 Unit Cell (moduli in GPa)

	No-sensor	Sensor 1 x 0.1 (mm)	Difference %
E ₁	34.42	36.34	5.58
E ₂	34.54	35.2	1.91
E ₃	6.60	6.85	3.79
G ₁₂	3.70	4.27	15.56
G ₁₃	1.49	1.53	2.67
G ₂₃	1.45	1.55	6.90
v ₁₂	0.048	0.053	10.42

Table 5 Comparison of No-sensor to Sensor-3 Unit Cell (moduli in GPa)

	No-sensor	Sensor 3.72 x 0.05 (mm)	Difference %
E ₁	34.42	36.46	5.93
E ₂	34.54	37.23	7.79
E ₃	6.60	6.98	5.76
G ₁₂	3.70	4.65	25.93
G ₁₃	1.49	1.54	3.36
G ₂₃	1.45	1.57	8.28
v ₁₂	0.048	0.067	39.58

It can be observed from Table 3 to Table 5 that predicted elastic properties increase with increase in the sensor size. For the sensor model (1x0.05mm), it can be found that the FE predicted Young's moduli (E_1 , E_2 and E_3) show a maximum increase of ~3% compared to the no-sensor model. Similarly, for the shear moduli (G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23}), the maximum increase is found to be around 9% compared to the no-sensor model.

Furthermore, it can be noticed that by doubling the thickness of the sensor (sensor-2 model), the maximum increase in the Young's moduli and Shear moduli is found to be approximately 5.6% and 16% respectively. Interestingly, it can be further noticed that for sensor-3 model, the maximum increase in Young's moduli is 8% and shear moduli is 26%.

VALIDATION OF UNIT CELL PROPERTIES

Modelling Parameters

For the unit cell model validation, a 2/2 twill weave unit cell model attached with the ribbon sensors has been considered as shown in Figure 7. The plain weave unit cell has not been used for validation because there was no available experimental data related to it. The model configuration of the twill weave is listed in Table 6. Hashin failure criterion [2] has been implemented in UMAT subroutine [1] for the failure strength prediction.

Figure 7 Yarn and Sensor in 2/2 Twill Weave Unit Cell Model

Table 6 Geometric Parameters (mm) for the 2/2 Twill Weave Unit Cell

	l	w	h	a	b
Unit cell	16.07	16.1	0.6	N/A	N/A
Warp/Weft Yarn	Sinusoidal and straight path [3]			0.2	3.96
Ribbon sensor	Following the yarn path	0.65	0.015	N/A	N/A

The input material properties for modelling are listed in Table 7 and Table 8. Based on the geometry considered for the twill weave unit cell, the total volume fraction of the

yarns has been estimated to be 52%. This value has been found to be in close agreement to the yarn volume fractions (55% ~ 58%) given by the test panel manufacturers.

Table 7 Elastic Material Properties in 2/2 Twill Weave Unit Cell (moduli in GPa)

	E ₁	E ₂	E ₃	G ₁₂	G ₁₃	G ₂₃	v ₁₂	v ₁₃	v ₂₃
Yarn	218	28.9	28.9	22.4	22.4	11.5	0.23	0.23	0.25
Matrix	3.46			1.28			0.35		
Sensor	100			38.46			0.3		

Table 8 Strength Properties (MPa) in 2/2 Twill Weave Unit Cell

	Tension			Compression			Shear		
	X _t	Y _t	Z _t	X _c	Y _c	Z _c	S ₁₂	S ₁₃	S ₂₃
Yarn	1744	52.6	52.6	1650	260	260	107.8	107.8	100
Matrix	60			250			50		
Sensor	1000~1700			N/A			N/A		

Predicted Results of Twill Weave Unit Cell

The predicted mechanical properties of the 2/2 twill weave unit cell model are listed in Table 9 and Table 10.

Table 9 Comparison of FE predicted Elastic Properties (moduli in GPa) for the No-sensor and Sensor Unit Cell Models

Properties	No-sensor	Sensor	Increase (%)
E _x (GPa)	67.19	67.37	0.27
E _y (GPa)	67.29	67.46	0.25
E _z (GPa)	9.19	9.35	0.5
G _{xy} (GPa)	12.07	12.1	0.25
G _{xz} (GPa)	2.72	2.73	0.37
G _{yz} (GPa)	2.72	2.73	0.37
v _{xy}	0.058	0.058	0
v _{xz}	0.384	0.383	-0.26
v _{yz}	0.384	0.383	-0.26

Table 10 Comparison of FE Predicted Strength Properties (MPa) for the No-sensor and Sensor Unit Cell Models

Properties (MPa)	No-sensor	Sensor	Difference (%)
X_t	386.2	390.62	1.14
Y_t	397.34	402.32	1.25
Z_t	68.45	68.39	-0.086
S_{xy}	62.34	62.57	0.36
S_{xz}	78.15	78.46	0.4
S_{yz}	78.15	78.46	0.4

It can be found from Table 9 that there is a slight difference between the results of the sensor and no-sensor model. The difference in the results is found to be less than 0.5% for moduli data and 1.3% for the strength data (Table 10).

Result Validation

The experimental data have been obtained for the 2/2 twill CF/epoxy woven laminates from the project partners [4] who fabricated and characterised the test panels. The comparison of the FE predicted and experimentally characterised properties are listed in the Table 11.

Table 11 Comparison of FE Predictions and Experimental Test Results

2/2 Twill Weave CF/epoxy	No-sensor			Sensor		
	Test	FE	Difference (%)	Test	FE	Difference (%)
Tensile modulus (GPa)	56.47	67.19	19	63.6	67.37	5.9
Poisson's ratio (in-plane)	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.064	0.058	-9.4
Tensile strength (MPa)	574.1	386.2	-32.7	441.78	390.6	-1.12
Interlaminar shear Strength (MPa)	64.49	66.45	3.03	46.72	66.7	42.8

From Table 11, it can be observed that the FE predicted tensile moduli are higher than those of the experimental results for both the No-sensor and Sensor model. In the case of strength predictions, it can be noticed that the predicted tensile strengths are lower than the experimental results. The lower tensile strength values could be related to Hashin failure criterion instead of usual maximum stress failure theory employed in the failure prediction. Interestingly, these results indicate that the FE predicted shear strength in the No-sensor model is in good agreement with the experimental value. On the other hand, the experimentally tested shear strength of the panel with sensors is

much lower than the FE predicted value. It has been noticed that the shear test specimens with sensors, on average, are 1.75 times thicker than those of No-sensors. This difference in the thicknesses could be one of the reasons for the discrepancy in the low shear moduli under short beam shear test.

It is understood that in the unit cell model with sensors, the sensors are in perfect bond with resin, therefore no decrease has been found in the predicted values compared to the predictions in the No-sensor model. While in reality, the sensors in laminate may act as defects which can induce de-bonding and may cause the property reductions.

SUMMARY

Plain weave and twill weave unit cell models have been performed to predict the elastic properties and strength of the woven composites with implementation of failure criterion. By assuming perfect bonding between sensor and woven composites in the model, the embedded sensors have shown to have slight influence on the mechanical properties of the woven composite. It can be noted that the sensor mechanical properties are greater than the resin and comparable to the yarns. Hence, the FE predicted mechanical properties have been found to increase with the increase in the sensor size. Comparing the predicted mechanical properties of the twill weave unit cell simulations to the experimental results, reasonable agreement has been found, except for the shear test corresponding to the composite panel containing the sensor. These test values show significant decrease of the shear strength in the composite panels containing the sensors. One of the reasons can be attributed to the misalignment of yarns in the sensed laminates during the manufacturing stage. Another possible reason could be that sensor and No-sensor panels being fabricated and characterised at different stages, this could have affected the consistency in the experimental results. Moreover, the reduction of the mechanical properties in FE simulations cannot be captured without the induction of interfacial mechanisms in the model.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Authors would like to thank Technology Strategy Board for rewarding the PRISM project and also thank the project partners: Sigmatex, QinetiQ, BVT group and Ellis Technology for their involvements in manufacturing textile preforms, sensing application and mechanical tests.

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